

**GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science:
Challenges in Higher Education**

Project Reference: 2024-1-ES01-KA220-HED-000246558

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Gender-Inclusive Educational Frameworks for LIS Curricula

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Gender Diversity in Information Science:

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Gender-Inclusive Educational Frameworks for LIS Curricula (WP2 Result 5)

Barcelona, 23/12/2025

UNIVERSITAT DE
BARCELONA

Citation: Boté-Vericad, Juan-José, Thomas Mandl, Dzejla Khattab, Michaela Dombrovska, Kornelija Petr-Balog and Stefan Dreisiebner. 2025. *Gender-Inclusive Educational Frameworks for LIS Curricula*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18098304

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1. Introduction

This report presents the gender-inclusive educational frameworks developed within Work Package 2 (WP2) of the Gender Diversity in Information Science: Challenges in Higher Education (GEDIS) project. Building on the curriculum analysis, expert consultations and training activities carried out in WP2, as well as on the prototype teaching packages and multilingual Open Educational Resources (OER) produced in the context of the ESSISGEN Summer School, the report proposes structured models for integrating gender perspectives into Library and Information Science (LIS) curricula. These frameworks are intended to support lecturers, programme coordinators and librarians who wish to embed gender equality and diversity in a systematic and sustainable manner across courses and learning pathways.

The document has three main objectives. First, it synthesises the insights emerging from WP2 Results 1–4 into a set of coherent educational frameworks that can be readily adopted or adapted by higher education institutions. Secondly, it demonstrates how the prototype teaching packages and OER can be aligned with existing modules at Bachelor and Master level, providing concrete examples of activities, assessment strategies and thematic blocks. Finally, it offers a reference point for subsequent work in the project, particularly for the piloting of innovations in WP4 and the development of professors' and librarians' toolkits in WP6.

This report presents three frameworks: Framework A, which focuses on gender-inclusive foundations of LIS; Framework B, which examines data, AI and gender in information environments; and Framework C, which addresses media, disinformation and gender in contemporary information environments. Each framework is accompanied by indicative learning outcomes, suggested combinations of OER and prototype teaching packages, and recommendations for adaptation in diverse institutional and national contexts. Together, they constitute the core output of WP2

Result 5 and provide a bridge between analytical work and practical implementation in GEDIS.

1.1. Anchor prototypes designed by teaching staff

This section summarises a set of anchor prototype teaching packages that were initially designed and led by teaching staff within the GEDIS consortium.

These prototypes draw on existing statistical data, methodological guidelines and analytic tools that are central for understanding gender in information science and related fields.

- Women in Science and Engineering in the EU (multilingual OER set based on Eurostat data; Boté-Vericad et al., 2025a).
- Global Gender Gap Report 2025 – World Economic Forum (suite of visual and textual OER interpreting key indicators; Boté-Vericad et al., 2025b).
- What Data Are You Collecting? Inclusive Perspectives in Gender-Focused Research (multilingual OER set; Boté-Vericad et al., 2025c).
- Delphi Method in Academic Research: A Step-by-Step Guide for Faculty Members (multilingual OER set; Boté-Vericad et al., 2025d).
- Curriculum Analysis Rubric – Gender Perspectives in Teaching Plans (rubric and accompanying explanatory material; Boté-Vericad et al., 2025e).

Together, these materials provide a strong empirical and methodological backbone for WP2 Result 3, offering robust, staff-curated resources that can be reused across the three educational frameworks described in this report.

1.2. Student co-created prototype teaching packages (ESSISGEN)

The gender-inclusive educational frameworks developed in WP2 build not only on staff-designed anchor prototypes, but also on a rich corpus of student co-created Open Educational Resources (OER). During the ESSISGEN Summer School in Barcelona, mixed international groups of students designed and tested OER that address gender issues in information, media and digital environments from diverse linguistic and cultural perspectives. These student-led contributions form a second layer of prototype teaching packages which complement and extend the staff anchor prototypes (Boté-Vericad, 2025; Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h).

The student co-created prototype teaching packages cover thematic clusters such as:

- paradoxes of media and information literacy (neutrality, trust, responsibility);
- user experience (UX) and human-computer interaction from a gender perspective;
- gender data gaps and algorithmic bias in artificial intelligence (*Mind the Gap* and related OER);
- gaming and gender in digital cultures;
- cultural heritage and gendered representations;
- translation and gender-sensitive linguistic mediation;
- intellectual freedom, censorship and access to knowledge;
- hate speech and mis/disinformation affecting women and marginalised groups;
- students' perceptions of using generative AI (ChatGPT) for educational purposes and gender differences.

Each of these clusters is documented in the WP2 Result 3 report on prototype teaching packages, where the constituent OER, learning outcomes and suggested activities are described in detail. In the present Result 5 report, these student co-created packages are integrated into the three gender-inclusive educational frameworks as flexible, multilingual teaching units that can be combined with staff anchor prototypes. This dual structure ensures that the frameworks remain grounded in real classroom and Summer School practices, while offering sufficient structure to support curriculum development at programme level.

2. Gender-Inclusive Educational Frameworks

On the basis of the curriculum analysis (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025f — Result 1), the consensus-building activities and tutorials (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025g — Result 2) and the prototype teaching packages (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h — Result 3), the consortium has developed three gender-inclusive educational frameworks for LIS curricula:

- Framework A – Gender-Inclusive Foundations of LIS (core and introductory courses)
- Framework B – Data, AI and Gender in Information Science
- Framework C – Media, Disinformation and Gender in Information Environments

Each framework offers a structured combination of blocks (topics, learning outcomes, activities and assessment), explicitly linked to multilingual OER and the prototype teaching packages produced in WP2. Together they show how gender perspectives can be systematically integrated into existing LIS courses and modules at Bachelor and Master level.

The frameworks are documented in the “GEDIS All OER and Frameworks Report (WP2)”, which provides detailed descriptions, suggested learning activities, examples of assessment, and guidance for adaptation to different institutional contexts. They have been discussed and refined with international teaching staff during the ESSISGEN Summer School in Barcelona and are ready to be used both for future piloting (e.g. Summer School in Opava, WP4) and for inclusion in the educational toolkit planned for this project (WP6).

2.1. Framework A – Gender-Inclusive Foundations of LIS

Title: Gender-Inclusive Foundations of Library and Information Science

Level: Undergraduate (2nd year)

Credits: 6 ECTS

Position: Core course in the LIS / Information Science degree

Overall aim: To introduce students to key concepts, functions and professional roles in LIS while systematically integrating gender perspectives into learning outcomes, content, examples, teaching methods and assessment.

Learning outcomes (selected, gender-integrated)

After completing the course, students will be able to:

- Explain core concepts and functions of Library and Information Science in contemporary societies.
- Identify how gender and other dimensions of diversity shape information needs, behaviours and access to information.

- Critically analyse information systems, services and media texts from a gender-aware perspective (e.g. UX design, metadata, search interfaces, AI tools).
- Reflect on the ethical responsibilities of LIS professionals in promoting gender equality and inclusive information practices.

2.1.1. Course structure and links to prototype teaching packages

Block 1 – Information, Media and Inequalities (Weeks 1–3)

Topics:

- Introduction to LIS and information landscapes
- Media and information literacy
- Inequalities in access and representation

Prototype teaching packages used (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h):

- Paradoxes of Media and Information Literacy
- Women in Science and Engineering in the EU

Example activities:

- Group discussion on paradoxes of media and information literacy using multilingual OER.
- Analysis of Eurostat-based OER on women in science and engineering; students interpret graphs and discuss implications for LIS services.

Block 2 – Users, UX and Gender (Weeks 4–5)

Topics:

- User studies and information behaviour from a gender-aware perspective.
- User experience (UX), accessibility and inclusive interface design in LIS environments.

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- Evaluation of discovery tools, catalogues and digital platforms with attention to gendered experiences.

Prototype teaching packages used (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h):

- User Experience: UX.
- Students' Perception on Using ChatGPT for Educational Purposes and Gender Differences.
- Paradoxes of Media and Information Literacy (optional, to link UX and media literacy).

Activities examples:

- Small-group evaluation of library or database interfaces using the UX and gender OER; students identify barriers and propose realistic improvements.
- Discussion of the ChatGPT perception OER; students compare their own experiences and identify possible gendered patterns in the use of generative AI.
- Students' Perception on Using ChatGPT for Educational Purposes and Gender Differences.

Block 3 – Data, AI and Gender (Weeks 6–8)

Topics:

- Data in LIS and digital platforms
- Gender data gaps and algorithmic bias
- AI tools in educational and professional settings

Prototype teaching packages used (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h):

- Mind the Gap: Gender Data and AI Bias
- Algorithmic Bias in AI: Key Concepts, Implications and Solutions

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Activities examples:

- Group analysis of mini-datasets or AI use cases, identifying where gender data are missing or biased.
- Class debate on the role of LIS professionals in mitigating algorithmic bias.

Block 4 – Media, Culture and Gender (Weeks 9–11)

Topics:

- Cultural heritage and memory institutions
- Representation of gender in collections and games
- Media narratives, stereotypes and inclusion

Prototype teaching packages used (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h):

- Cultural Heritage and Gender
- Gaming and Gender

Activities examples:

- Students examine online collections or catalogues and discuss how women and gender-diverse groups are represented.
- Analysis of selected game descriptions or screenshots with the Gaming & Gender OER; reflection on implications for media literacy.

Block 5 – Professional Ethics and Inclusive Practice (Weeks 12–13)

Topics:

- Professional codes of ethics in LIS
- Hate speech, mis/disinformation and gender

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- Inclusive language, translation and metadata

Prototype teaching packages used (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h):

- Hate Speech & Mis/Disinformation and Women
- Translation and Gender

Activities examples:

- Case-based discussion on hate speech and mis/disinformation affecting women and gender minorities.
- Short translation/rewriting exercise where students adapt titles, abstracts or metadata to make them more inclusive.

Assessment

Continuous assessment (60 %):

- Short reflection pieces linked to selected prototype activities (e.g. UX analysis, AI bias case, cultural heritage exercise).
- Group presentation on one thematic block, showing how gender has been integrated into an LIS-related problem.

Final assignment (40 %):

Students select one LIS service (library, archive, digital platform) and write a 2.000–2.500-word essay or project report analysing it from a gender-inclusive perspective and proposing realistic improvements.

Guidelines for educators

Educators may choose fewer blocks depending on available time, but are encouraged to include at least three prototype teaching packages and explicit gender-related learning outcomes. OER can be used in any of the consortium languages; bilingual or multilingual classes can exploit the availability of several versions. The framework is flexible: it can be implemented in a full 6 ECTS course or adapted into a 3 ECTS module by reducing the number of blocks. Reflection on local context is key: educators are invited to complement the prototype teaching packages with national/regional examples and institutional policies.

2.2. Framework B – Data, AI and Gender in Information Science

Title: Data, AI and Gender in Information Science

Level: Undergraduate (final year) or Master's level

Credits: 3–6 ECTS

Position: Elective or specialisation module within LIS, Information Science, Data Science or related programmes

Overall aim: To examine how data practices and artificial intelligence systems intersect with gender inequalities, and to equip students with conceptual and practical tools to recognise, analyse and mitigate gender-related biases in data-intensive information environments.

Learning outcomes (gender-integrated)

After completing this course, students will be able to:

- Explain key concepts related to gender data gaps, algorithmic bias and fairness in AI-driven information systems.
- Interpret and critically discuss statistical indicators and reports on gender inequalities in science, engineering and the information sector.
- Analyse datasets, algorithms and digital services used in LIS and related domains from a gender-aware perspective.
- Propose realistic strategies for designing and implementing gender-sensitive data practices and AI applications in LIS settings.

2.2.1. Course structure and links to prototype teaching packages

Block 1 – Gender, Data and Inequalities in Knowledge Production (Weeks 1–2)

Topics:

- Gender as a category in statistics and data collection
- Structural gender inequalities in science, technology and information professions
- Limits and possibilities of quantitative indicators

Prototype teaching packages used (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h):

- Women in Science and Engineering in the EU
- Global Gender Gap Report 2025 OER set

Activities examples:

1. Students work in pairs with the OER on women in science and engineering, exploring Eurostat and related visualisations. They identify patterns by country,

sector and age and discuss how these patterns relate to LIS and information infrastructures.

2. In groups, students analyse selected figures from the Global Gender Gap Report 2025 and prepare short posters explaining what the indicators reveal and what they hide.

Block 2 – Gender Data Gaps and Their Consequences (Weeks 3–4)

Topics:

- The concept of gender data gaps (missing data, under-representation, biased categories)
- Consequences for research, policy and digital services
- Relevance for LIS (collections, catalogues, user statistics, usage data)

Prototype teaching packages used (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h):

- Mind the Gap: Gender Data and AI Bias
- What Data Are You Collecting? Inclusive Perspectives in Gender-Focused Research

Activities examples:

1. Using the Mind the Gap OER, students analyse simplified datasets where gender variables are incomplete or poorly coded. They discuss how decisions about data collection shape what can be known and who is visible.
2. Students examine their own institution's data collection practices (for example, library statistics, course evaluation forms) and use the What Data Are You Collecting? OER to propose improvements from an inclusive, gender-sensitive perspective.

Block 3 – Algorithmic Bias in AI Systems (Weeks 5–7)

Topics:

- Types of bias in algorithmic systems (data, model, interaction, feedback loops)
- Examples in search engines, recommendation systems, ranking algorithms and recruitment tools
- Ethical frameworks, accountability and responsibility

Prototype teaching packages used (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h):

- Algorithmic Bias in AI: Key Concepts, Implications and Solutions
- Selected cases from Mind the Gap package (optional)

Activities examples:

1. In small groups, students analyse public cases of algorithmic bias (e.g. job advertisement systems, image recognition, content moderation) guided by the OER on algorithmic bias.
2. Each group prepares a short “bias audit” of a chosen digital service (library discovery tool, database, streaming platform, social network), identifying potential gender-related issues and suggesting mitigation strategies.

Block 4 – Generative AI, Education and Gender (Weeks 8–9)

Topics:

- Generative AI tools (such as ChatGPT) in educational contexts
- Student practices, risks and opportunities
- Gendered patterns in adoption, perceived usefulness and concerns

Prototype teaching packages used:

- Students' Perception on Using ChatGPT for Educational Purposes and Gender Differences (plus translations)

Activities examples:

1. Students read the OER and compare the findings with their own experiences via a short anonymous in-class poll.
2. Small-group discussion on how gender, discipline and language shape students' uses of generative AI, followed by a plenary reflection on the implications for LIS education and academic support services.

Block 5 – Open Data, Transparency and Trust (Weeks 10–11)

Topics:

- Open data in public administration and science
- Transparency, accountability and trust, with a focus on gender-related data
- LIS roles in mediating and curating open data

Prototype teaching packages used (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h):

- Open Data: Transparency vs. Trust
- What Data Are You Collecting? Inclusive Perspectives in Gender-Focused Research (revisited)

Activities examples:

1. Students use the open data OER to evaluate a real open data portal (local, national, European), focusing on the availability and quality of gender-related datasets.
2. Group assignment: design a short data story or infographic highlighting a gender-related issue using open data, and discuss how LIS professionals could support similar initiatives.

Block 6 – Designing Gender-Aware Data and AI Practices in LIS (Week 12–13)

Topics:

- Integrating insights from previous blocks into professional practice
- Designing guidelines or policies for LIS organisations
- Preparing for future professional roles

Prototype teaching packages used (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h):

- Any relevant packages from previous blocks (students choose)

Activities examples:

1. Final group project: students develop a brief proposal for implementing gender-aware data and AI practices in a specific LIS context (academic library, public library, archive, information centre), explicitly referencing concepts and OER used in the course.
2. Peer feedback session where groups present their proposals and receive comments from peers and the lecturer.

Assessment

Continuous assessment (60 %):

Short written assignments linked to Blocks 1–4 (interpretation of indicators, mini bias-audit, reflection on ChatGPT perceptions, critique of data practices). Group presentation (Block 5 or 6) on an open data or AI-related case, including gender-sensitive analysis.

Final project (40 %):

Group or individual project report (2,500–3,000 words) designing a gender-aware data/AI intervention or guideline for a chosen LIS setting, with explicit reference to course concepts and OER.

Guidelines for educators

Educators may select a subset of blocks depending on credit load, but are encouraged to include at least: one block on gender indicators/data gaps, one block on algorithmic bias, and one block on generative AI and student practices. The course can be taught in any consortium language, using the multilingual OER. Educators are invited to supplement the prototype teaching packages with local examples (national reports, institutional policies, national court cases or media coverage of AI incidents). The framework can also be reduced to a 3 ECTS module by selecting four blocks and merging the final design project into continuous assessment.

2.3. Framework C – Media, Disinformation and Gender in Information Environments

Title: Media, Disinformation and Gender in Information Environments

Level: Undergraduate (3rd–4th year) or Master’s level

Credits: 3–6 ECTS

Position: Elective course in LIS, Communication, Media Studies or Information and Communication Sciences

Overall aim: To explore how media, digital games, cultural heritage and translation practices shape gendered representations and experiences in contemporary

information environments, with a particular focus on disinformation, hate speech and epistemic injustice, and to develop critical and practical competences to address these issues in LIS-related contexts.

Learning outcomes (gender-integrated)

After completing this course, students will be able to:

- Describe key concepts related to media and information literacy, disinformation, hate speech and epistemic injustice from a gender perspective.
- Critically analyse media texts, games, cultural heritage materials and translations that contribute to or challenge gender stereotypes and inequalities.
- Identify gendered dynamics in mis/disinformation campaigns and hate speech, including their historical and political dimensions.
- Design and justify small-scale educational or informational interventions (e.g. OER, activities, communication pieces) that counter harmful narratives and promote more inclusive representations.

2.3.1. Course structure and links to prototype teaching packages

Block 1 – Media and Information Literacy with a Gender Lens (Weeks 1–2)

Topics:

- Media and information literacy (MIL) concepts
- Paradoxes of being “well informed” in digital societies
- Gender and other inequalities in MIL

Prototype teaching packages used (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h):

- Paradoxes of Media and Information Literacy (multilingual OER set)

Activities examples:

1. Students work in small groups with different language versions of the OER and identify how MIL paradoxes manifest in their own media habits, paying attention to gendered experiences.
2. Plenary mapping of paradoxes on a whiteboard (e.g. overload vs ignorance, visibility vs invisibility), with examples that highlight gender dimensions.

Block 2 – Gaming, Popular Culture and Gender (Weeks 3–4)

Topics:

- Video games and interactive media as information/learning environments
- Representation of gender in games and gaming cultures
- Stereotypes, harassment, inclusion and resistance

Prototype teaching packages used (Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h):

- Gaming and Gender

Activities examples:

1. In groups, students analyse game covers, trailers or gameplay clips using the Gaming & Gender OER as a framework (characters, roles, narratives, mechanics).
2. Short written or video reflections where students discuss how games can reinforce or subvert gender norms, and what role LIS professionals could play in curating game collections or designing game-based learning with a gender perspective.

Block 3 – Cultural Heritage, Memory and Gender (Weeks 5–6)

Topics:

- GLAM institutions (galleries, libraries, archives, museums) and cultural memory
- Visibility/invisibility of women and gender-diverse people in collections
- Historical depictions of gender roles

Prototype teaching packages used:

- Cultural Heritage and Gender
- Old Engravings – Reflecting on Gender Roles Throughout History OER set

Activity examples:

1. Students explore digitised collections or the “Old Engravings” OER and identify how gender roles are represented in specific historical periods.
2. Group activity designing a short thematic virtual exhibition or curated selection (e.g. using images and short texts) that offers a more inclusive lens on historical materials.

Block 4 – Hate Speech, Mis/Disinformation and Socialist Contexts (Weeks 7–9)

Topics:

- Definitions and typologies of hate speech and disinformation
- Gendered targeting in mis/disinformation campaigns
- Historical and ideological dimensions, including socialist contexts
- Roles of LIS institutions and professionals

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Prototype teaching packages used:

- Hate Speech & Mis/Disinformation: The Real Status or Treatment of Women within Socialist Contexts (and its multilingual variants)

Activity examples:

1. Students analyse selected examples (texts, posts, headlines) that illustrate gendered hate speech or disinformation, guided by the OER.
2. Small-group mapping of narratives (e.g. about women, feminists, LGBTQ+ communities) used in mis/disinformation, and discussion of how these narratives connect to broader political and historical contexts.
3. Class discussion on the challenges for libraries and archives in documenting, preserving and countering such materials.

Block 5 – Translation, Language and Epistemic Justice (Weeks 10–11)

Topics:

- Translation as a knowledge practice
- Gender and language: grammatical gender, inclusive language, erasure
- Epistemic injustice and linguistic mediation

Prototype teaching packages used:

- Translation and Gender (multilingual)

Activity examples:

1. Students compare original and translated versions of short texts (titles, abstracts, catalogue records or media descriptions) and identify where gendered meanings are lost, softened or introduced.

2. Guided rewriting exercise in which students propose more inclusive and accurate translations or descriptions, followed by a reflection on power and responsibility in translation and metadata work.

Block 6 – Designing Educational and Informational Interventions (Week 12–13)

Topics:

- From critical analysis to action
- Designing small-scale interventions for media and information literacy, GLAM programmes or community projects
- Using OER and open licensing to maximise impact

Prototype teaching packages used:

- Any of the above, as chosen by student groups

Activity examples:

1. Final project: student groups design an educational activity, mini-OER, exhibition concept or communication campaign addressing a specific gender-related issue in media, games, cultural heritage or translation.
2. Each group prepares a short implementation plan (target audience, objectives, activities, required resources, evaluation ideas) and presents it in class.

Assessment

Continuous assessment (60 %):

Short reflection pieces after Blocks 1–3 (MIL paradoxes, gaming analysis, cultural heritage exercise). Participation in class discussions and group work, including contributions to the mapping of narratives and rewriting tasks.

Final project (40 %):

Group project that combines one or more prototype teaching packages into a concrete intervention (educational resource, exhibition outline, workshop concept, small campaign), accompanied by a written rationale (1,500–2,000 words) explaining the gender perspective, intended impact and role of LIS/GLAM professionals.

Guidelines for educators

Educators may adapt the examples and case materials to their national or institutional context, while using the prototype OER as a conceptual and structural backbone. The course can be reshaped into a shorter module by focusing on four of the six blocks, or extended by adding local case studies, guest speakers or visits to GLAM institutions. The multilingual nature of many OER allows for comparative exercises across languages and cultures; educators are encouraged to exploit this for critical reflection on translation and representation. The framework is suitable both for LIS programmes and for broader Communication/Media Studies curricula, and can be adapted to online or blended formats by using digital collaboration tools and virtual exhibitions.

3. OER basis for the gender-inclusive educational frameworks

The three gender-inclusive educational frameworks presented in this report are grounded in a substantial corpus of multilingual Open Educational Resources (OER) produced within WP2. This corpus includes both staff-designed anchor prototypes and student co-created OER developed during the ESSISGEN Summer School in Barcelona. Together, these materials provide the concrete content, case studies and activities that make the frameworks operational in real teaching contexts.

The OER families underpinning the frameworks cover, among others, the following thematic clusters:

- Paradoxes of media and information literacy (neutrality, trust, responsibility).
- User experience (UX) and human-computer interaction from a gender perspective.
- Gender data gaps and algorithmic bias in artificial intelligence (*Mind the Gap* and related resources).
- Gaming and gender in digital cultures.
- Cultural heritage and gendered representations in GLAM institutions.
- Translation and gender-sensitive linguistic mediation.
- Intellectual freedom, censorship and access to knowledge.
- Hate speech and mis/disinformation affecting women and marginalised groups.
- Women in science and engineering in the EU.
- Inclusive approaches to data collection and research design in gender-focused studies.

The detailed description of the twelve prototype teaching packages, including full OER lists, DOIs, learning outcomes and suggested activities, is provided in the Prototype Teaching Packages Report (WP2 Result 3; Boté-Vericad et al., 2025h) and in the GEDIS All OER Report – ESSISGEN Summer School Barcelona (Boté-Vericad, 2025). In the present Result 5 report, these packages are not reproduced in full; instead, they are integrated into Frameworks A, B and C as modular units that can be combined and adapted to different courses and institutional contexts.

4. Conclusions and future use of frameworks

This report documents WP2 Result 5 by presenting a coherent set of gender-inclusive educational frameworks for Library and Information Science curricula. The three frameworks – *Gender-Inclusive Foundations of LIS, Data, AI and Gender in Information Science and Media, Disinformation and Gender in Information Environments* – synthesise insights from the curriculum analysis, the Consensus Document on Innovative Teaching Strategies and the prototype teaching packages developed in WP2. Together, they show how gender perspectives can be embedded systematically across core, thematic and methodological components of LIS programmes, rather than being confined to isolated optional modules.

The frameworks are designed to be modular and adaptable. Each framework groups staff-designed anchor prototypes and student co-created prototype teaching packages into logically structured blocks, with clear learning outcomes, suggested assessment approaches and links to typical courses (e.g. information literacy, UX, data and society, research methods). This modularity allows programme coordinators and individual lecturers to adopt the frameworks incrementally, aligning them with local curricular structures, institutional priorities and national regulations.

Looking ahead, the three frameworks will be further tested and refined in subsequent project activities. In particular, selected blocks and prototype teaching packages will be piloted in the ESSISGEN Summer School in Opava and in regular courses across partner institutions (WP4), using the *Detailed Implementation and Evaluation Plan* developed as WP2 Result 4. The frameworks will also constitute a core component of the professors' and librarians' toolkits to be produced in WP6, where they will be accompanied by practical guidance, checklists and examples of good practice.

Beyond the lifetime of the project, the gender-inclusive educational frameworks offer a transferable model for other LIS schools and GLAM institutions seeking to advance

gender equality in teaching and curriculum design. By combining multilingual OER, prototype teaching packages and a clear curricular architecture, they provide a sustainable basis for continuing innovation, institutional learning and cross-European collaboration on gender and information science.

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**GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science:
Challenges in Higher Education**

Project Reference: 2024-1-ES01-KA220-HED-000246558
<https://ub.edu/GEDIS>

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